

MICRO-MACRO APPROACH FOR PREDICTING LOCALIZED STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN COMPOSITES

S. Gupta¹, G. Soni^{2*}, R. Singh¹

¹ Mechanical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai, India,

² Mechanical Engineering, IITB-Monash Research academy, Mumbai, India

* Corresponding author (ganesh.soni@iitb.ac.in)

Keywords: *partial homogenization, multi-scale method, fiber-matrix debonding*

1 General Introduction

The application of composite materials in structural design has tremendously increased over the years. Typically, aircraft and automobile industries utilize composites for the production of several critical components which require superior properties for their proper functioning. The extensive utility of composites is attributed to their high strength-to-weight ratios and also high stiffness-to-weight ratios. The design of composite structures requires complete understanding of mechanical behavior of composites under various loading conditions and the key factor behind prediction of failure of such components is the knowledge of global as well as local damage response. Often, failure in composites originates from stress concentration regions in the structure. For example, an aircraft wing consists of ribs with flanged cut-outs for the passage of fuel and weight reduction and the stress concentration at these cut-outs leads to failure of the ribs at lower loads than estimated. In order to characterize this failure, evaluation of actual distribution of stresses in these regions is essential. A macroscopic analysis of the entire structure considering it as a continuum would give the distribution of stresses around the stress concentration region but the stress obtained wouldn't be actual stresses owing to the extreme heterogeneity of composites. Hence, it is imperative to carry out a microscale analysis of the structure modeling all the heterogeneities. A direct consequence of the inclusion of all the microstructural details in the structure is the inevitable complexity and massive computational cost. To avoid this redundancy of microstructural analysis, models based on Representative Volume Element (RVE) and multiscale methods are developed to obtain the microstress distribution in the structure. The models based on RVE utilize periodic boundary conditions holds invalid in the

regions of stress singularities. Hence, a different multiscale modeling approach has been proposed in this work which can overcome this limitation of the existing RVE approach.

2 Multiscale modeling approaches for composite materials

In recent years it has been established that the multiscale modeling strategy is needed for homogenization of engineering materials while retaining important small-scale details. In multiscale modeling, macroscopic and microscopic models are coupled to take advantage of the efficiency of macroscopic models and the accuracy of the microscopic models. The scope of such multiscale modeling is to design combined microscopic-macroscopic computational methods that are more efficient than solving the full microscopic model and at the same time give the information that we need to the desired accuracy. Ghosh et. al [1] proposed a coupled multiscale two-dimensional model for heterogeneous linear elastic structures. Homogenized material coefficients for a global displacement finite element model are generated by Voronoi Cell Finite Element Method (VCFEM) analysis using periodic boundary conditions on the base cell, i.e., the microstructure cell containing all the inclusions and voids modeled exclusively. Following the macroscopic analysis, the local VCFEM analysis is implemented at a macro structural point by using the global strains to depict the true evolution of microstructural stresses and strains. A FE based multiscale model was introduced by Feyel [2] called FE². In this method, the macroscopic analysis is performed using the homogenization of the periodic media. A RVE is assigned to each integration point at the macroscopic scale and a separate finite element computation is

performed at the microscale simultaneously. This method assumes that all points in the structure are periodic and micro-scale and macro-scale is properly separated from one another, i.e., the micro-structure is very small as compared to macro-structure. However, the assumption of periodicity is lost at the points close to free edges or points of high stress concentration, and thus this approach cannot be used in these areas. Markovic and Ibrahimbegovic [3] proposed a two-scale computational strategy for modeling the inelastic behavior of heterogeneous materials. Finite element method was applied to the structural scale as well as on the micro scale. The special care is taken in handling the interface condition between micro and macro scales. Gonzalez and Llorca [4] simulated the fracture behavior of a fiber-reinforced composite beam in the presence of a notch perpendicular to the fibers by means of a multiscale model based on an embedded cell approach in three dimensions. The representation of the material in front of the notch tip, where damage is concentrated included the actual fiber/matrix topology in the composite, while the rest of the beam was represented by a linear thermoelastic, transversally isotropic homogeneous solid. These multiscale methods provide accurate results at both microscopic and macroscopic length scales. Multi-level method proposed by Sun and Wang [5] is a two-level macro-micro approach in which the effective properties derived from the laminate theories are utilized to predict the effective (macroscopic) stress and effective (macroscopic) displacement fields. Subsequently, the area of interest (e.g., stress concentration area), is modeled at micro-scale i.e. with actual fibers, matrix and interface. Macro-stresses and/or macro-displacements are used along with the micro-scale domain as boundary condition. They proposed a “local domain test”, which states that, if the micro-stresses in the area of the interest is very small, the domain selected for micro-scale modeling in two-level analysis is sufficient. Wang and Yan [6] proposed an inter-scale theory for the onset of matrix-dominated tensile failures in unidirectional and multi-directional laminates loaded globally. The theory utilizes the macro-field of the laminate obtained after homogenization to recover the micro field at fiber and matrix scale (de-homogenization). It is against this backdrop that an attempt is made to formulate a multiscale scheme which is

computationally viable but also accurate in inelastic regions. In the present work, it is intended to extend the idea of homogenization and de-homogenization by Wang and Yan [6] and club it with the idea of partial homogenization provided by Borokov et. al [7] for the formulation of a multi-scale scheme which can be utilized to accurately obtain the micro-stress fields in the regions of high stress concentrations. A region of interest (or a local domain) is firstly identified in the structure which is generally points of stress concentration, edges, crack tips etc. and is replaced by the microstructure of the composite, i.e., randomly distributed fibers in the matrix. The rest of the structure is still modeled as a homogeneous continuum with effective properties. Strong kinematic coupling is incorporated between the local domain and the homogeneous continuum. This modified structure, i.e., the original structure along with the modified local domain is then solved and the required micro-stresses in the region of interest are obtained.

The objective of this paper is to compare the local damage mechanisms operating close to stress singularities with those operating away from the singularities. The paper is divided into 7 sections and the layout of the paper is as follows: In Section 3, the main operating principle behind the micro-macro scheme is explained. The finite element geometry, material models used and the applied boundary conditions are explained in Section 4. In Section 5, the model is validated by comparing the shear response of a cross-ply laminate predicted by this scheme with the experimental response of the laminate determined through V-notched rail shear test [8]. The results and the parameter sensitivity analysis along with the micro-macro analysis at the notch root are also described in this section. The obtained numerical results are discussed in detailed in Section 6. Section 7 presents a concise summary of the results obtained and the conclusions drawn in this work.

3 Locality Principle

The locality principle states that the effect of homogenization of the structure has an influence on the homogenized part no farther than the characteristic length of the structure [7]. As a direct application of this principle, one can model the

microstructure in only a very small region of interest in the macrostructure e.g., crack tip, stress raisers etc. and keep the remaining structure as a homogeneous material. Fig.1 shows the 2D model of a partially homogenized lamina under transverse tension. The portion of the lamina which is shown as the microstructure consists of the matrix and fibers and the rest of the lamina is modeled as a continuous homogeneous material medium with effective properties. Fig. 2 shows the σ_{yy} distribution around the center fiber of a lamina composed entirely of matrix and fibers and a partially homogenized lamina under transverse tension. It is clearly evident from Fig. 2 that the stress distribution around the center fiber under same loading conditions in both the cases is similar, which depicts the validity of the locality principle. This principle is exploited to formulate the micro-macro method with the objective of obtaining the actual microstress fields in the regions of stress concentration.

Fig. 1. Partially homogenized lamina with the microstructure in transverse tension

Mathematically, the problem of coupling macro-fields with micro-fields can be compared to the problem of coupling a single spring with multiple springs. A global load is applied on one end of the single spring and it causes the deformation of the remaining springs. The springs here are rigidly coupled and the single spring represents the "macro-structure" and the multiple springs represent the "micro-structure", whose degrees of freedom are more than that of the macrostructure because of discretization of different length scales. Fig. 3 depicts the spring equivalents representation of the micro- macro scheme.

Fig. 2. Figure showing the σ_{yy} distribution around the center fiber for both cases

Fig. 3. The overall scheme represented by spring equivalents

4 Finite element description

4.1 Model geometry

The scheme requires the modeling of both the structure and the microstructure. The geometry of the structure is similar to the geometry of the specimen used in ASTM D7078 standard [8]. The actual specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 4(a). The specimen contains a double V-notch and most of the part of the specimen to the right and left of the V-shaped notches is clamped tightly during the experiment. Therefore in order to save computational power these sections are not included in the model geometry. This can be seen in Fig. 4(b) which provides the details of the geometry of the structure used in the model.

The microstructure consists of two cubical cells with fibers in one cell oriented orthogonally with respect to fibers in the other cell. Each cell contains randomly distributed fibers in the matrix with a volume fraction of 28%. The fiber diameter is $24 \mu\text{m}$ and 24 fibers are modeled within a cube of side

measuring 0.2 mm and composed up of matrix material. The size of the cube containing matrix material is constrained by the available computational power but is chosen large enough to capture all the relevant microstructural details. Cohesive elements with zero thickness are introduced between the outside surface of a fiber and the surrounding matrix in order to capture the influence of the interfacial properties on the mechanical behavior of the laminate. The detailed geometry of the microstructure is as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Figure showing (a) actual specimen geometry (b) model geometry

Fig. 5. The geometry of the microstructural domain

Fig. 6 shows how the microstructure is modeled with the structure by making an orthogonal slot in the structure. The position of the slot is chosen arbitrarily and the results obtained by placing the slot at a different position in the structure are presented in Section 5. Fig. 6 shows the magnified view of the section of the structure which is cut by the plane of symmetry PQRS and contains the line AB. The position of the slot with reference to the structure is clearly illustrated by a cross sectional view of the slot in the plane PQRS. The slot is symmetric about the line AB and the plane PQRS. The dimensions of the slot are 0.2 mm X 0.2mm X

0.4mm. The microstructure is placed in the niche as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Geometry of the unified specimen and microstructure

4.2 Material

The macrostructure is considered to be a homogeneous unidirectional elastic lamina under plane stress conditions and the stiffness values are provided in Table 1 as given by laminate theory.

Table 1: Elastic properties of the lamina

$E_{11}(\text{GPa})$	$E_{22}(\text{GPa})$	$G_{12}(\text{GPa})$	ν_{12}
23.8	6.368	2.2	0.2804

Table 2: Elastic properties of fiber and matrix

Material	$E(\text{GPa})$	$G(\text{GPa})$	ν
Epoxy resin Epofine-556/fine hardener-951	4.1	2.08	0.3
E-glass, $\rho_L=4800 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $d=24\mu\text{m}$	73	29.67	0.23

E-glass (ER-459L) fibers were modeled as linear elastic isotropic solids and their constants are given in Table 2. The epoxy matrix (EPOFINE-556) with FINEHARD-951 hardener was assumed to behave as an isotropic, elasto-plastic material and its elastic constants are also provided in Table 2. The plastic deformation was governed by multi-axial Mohr-Coulomb criterion. The Mohr-Coulomb criterion described in Jiang and Xie [9] considers that yielding takes place when the shear stress, τ , acting on a specific plane reaches a critical value, which is a function of the normal stress, σ_n acting on that plane, as indicated in Eq. (1). The corresponding

yield surface, written in terms of the maximum and minimum principal stresses (σ_1 and σ_3) is given by Eq. (2).

$$|\tau| = c + \sigma_n \tan \varphi \quad (1)$$

$$F(\sigma_1, \sigma_3) = (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) + (\sigma_1 + \sigma_3) \sin \varphi - 2c \cos \varphi \quad (2)$$

where c and φ are matrix cohesion and the matrix friction angle respectively. The matrix tensile strength, $\sigma_{mt} = 75$ MPa and $\sigma_{mc} = 105$ MPa have been measured experimentally and used for the calculation of c and φ :

$$\sigma_{mt} = 2c \frac{\cos \varphi}{1 + \sin \varphi}, \quad \sigma_{mc} = 2c \frac{\cos \varphi}{1 - \sin \varphi} \quad (3)$$

The fiber-matrix interfacial decohesion was simulated using standard cohesive surface elements in ABAQUS Standard[®]. The mechanical behavior of the interface was simulated using a traction-separation law which relates the displacement across the interface to the force vector acting on it. In the absence of any damage, the interface behavior was assumed to be linear with high value of an initial stiffness, K (10 GPa/mm) to ensure the displacement continuity at the interface. The linear behavior ends at the onset of damage, using a maximum stress criteria expressed as:

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{N}, \frac{t_s}{S} \right\} = 1 \quad (4)$$

Here, t_n and t_s are normal and tangential stresses transferred by the interface, respectively. t_n is positive or zero otherwise, because compressive normal stresses do not cause opening of the crack. N and S are the normal and tangential interfacial strengths, assumed to be equal for simplicity. Fracture energy, Γ , is another parameter which controls the interface behavior other than cohesive strength (N, S). The interface failure model assumes that the energy consumed during the fracture of the interface is independent of the loading path. Fracture energy, Γ is described as

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} t \Delta \delta \quad (5)$$

where t (t_n or t_s) is the cohesive strength of the interface and ' δ ' is the displacement across the interface. The damage evolution of the interface was displacement controlled and linear as shown in the Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Standard traction-separation law

4.3 Meshing

Fig. 8. Mesh convergence analysis of the structure. The legend shows the relative number of elements around the microstructure

The mesh density in the structure was varied from coarse to very fine around the microstructure. The numbers of elements in the structural mesh were progressively increased to establish convergence in the results as shown in Fig. 8. The curves drop down from curve-1 to curve-80 as the mesh density around the microstructure is increased and ultimately converge to curve-80. SC8R continuum shell elements were used to discretize the structure.

C3D8R 3D solid elements were used for discretizing fiber and matrix. COH3D8 cohesive elements were used for the modeling of interface. A total number of 142526 elements and 157265 nodes were used in the model.

4.4 Boundary conditions on the structure

The boundary conditions applied on the structure are illustrated in Fig. 9. Since the loading applied on the specimen is purely in plane shear, the face ABPQ is fixed and U_x is set to zero on the opposite face DCRS. The structure is loaded by giving some arbitrary positive displacement δ_0 to the face DCRS and setting U_y to δ_0 . U_z is set to zero for the two faces ABCD and PQRS so as to obtain the in-plane properties. Displacement controlled loading was used, the load carried by the structure decreases as the structure fails which allows for a slower rate of failure.

Fig. 9. Figure showing the boundary conditions on the structure for in-plane shear

4.5 Coupling between microstructure and macrostructure

The connection between the microstructure and macrostructure has been established through kinematic constraints which can define linear or non-linear relations between the nodes of the microstructure and macrostructure. The constraint type used in this work is surface-based tie constraint, in which each node on the first surface (the slave surface) will have the same values for its degrees of freedom as the point on the second surface (the master surface) to which it is closest. The master

surfaces are selected from the macrostructure geometry and the corresponding to each master surface one slave surface is selected from the microstructure geometry.

5 Results

5.1 Model validation

Fig. 10 shows the experimental response along with the $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ vs $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ curves predicted by micro-macro scheme. Throughout this section, $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ refer to the in-plane shear stress and in-plane shear strain averaged over the volume of the microstructure unless mentioned otherwise.

Fig. 10. Comparison between experimental and response predicted by micro-macro scheme

5.2 Parameter sensitivity analysis

5.2.1 Effect of interface strength

The strength of the interface between the fiber and matrix plays a important role in determining the interface properties such as onset of debonding. The $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ vs $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ curves predicted by this micro-macro scheme are plotted in Fig. 11 for three different [0/90] composite laminates with interface strength varying from 5-30 MPa. Fig. 11 shows that the response remains unaffected by the change in the strength values until the point where the interface failure takes place. Once the interface is degraded the load transfer from the matrix to the fibers reduces leading to lesser average stress for a given strain in the microstructural volume consisting fibers and matrix. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 11

wherein the curve for interface with 10 MPa strength drops below the curve of the interface with 30 MPa strength after a strain of ~3%. It was observed that beyond a value of the interface strength between 10-15MPa, there was no damage initiation in the cohesive elements for strains less than 4%.

Fig. 11. The effect of changing strength of the fiber-matrix interface ($c = 10$ MPa)

5.2.2 Effect of interface stiffness

Fig. 12. The effect of changing stiffness of a strong interface ($K = 10$ GPa/mm)

The $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ vs $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ curves predicted by this micro-macro scheme are plotted in Figs. 12 and 13 for three different [0/90] composite laminates with interface stiffness varying from 10-35 GPa/mm. The stiffness is varied for both weak and strong interface, with the strength for the strong interface as 30 MPa

while for the weak interface, strength was kept at 10 MPa. The results for the strong interface in Fig. 12 clearly illustrate that a stiffer interface results in higher average stresses. In Fig. 13, it is however seen that the curve corresponding to 15 GPa/mm stiffness drops down below the 10 GPa/mm curve after ~2.5 % strain. This happens because the interface failure in the laminate with higher interface stiffness occurs prior to that with lower stiffness since the traction separation curve for the interface is linear and the strength is same in both cases. Now since the interface fails, the average stresses would decrease.

Fig. 13. The effect of changing stiffness of a weak interface ($K = 10$ GPa/mm)

5.2.3 Effect of matrix friction angle

The $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ vs $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ curves predicted by this micro-macro scheme are plotted in Figs. 14, 15 for three different [0/90] composite laminates with matrix friction angles ranging from 5° to 15° . Since the matrix tensile strength was assumed to be constant and equal to 75 MPa, changes in the friction angles modifies the cohesive strength 'c' of the matrix as given in Eq. 3. The cohesive strength of the matrix increases from 37.5 MPa ($\phi=0^\circ$) up to 48.8 MPa ($\phi=15^\circ$). As can be seen from the Figs. 14,15 that the onset of non-linear behaviour is affected by changing the friction angle in both strong as well as weak interface. A lower value of friction angle leads to earlier onset of matrix yielding because the cohesive strength reduces when the friction angle is decreased and the resistance to shear deformation decreases.

Fig. 14. The effect of changing matrix friction angle with a strong interface

Fig. 15. The effect of changing matrix friction angle with a weak interface

5.3 Micro-macro analysis at the notch root

Fig. 16. The position of the microstructure near the notch root

Fig. 16 shows the position of the slot near the notch root and how the microstructure is placed in it. Fig. 17 shows $\langle \tau_{12} \rangle$ vs $\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle$ curves at the notch and regions away from the notch. It is clearly

evident that there is negligible difference between the local shear response at the notch root and at regions away from the notch. This shows that the composite laminate material response is unaffected by the stress singularities and is comparable to the response away from them notch root.

Fig. 17. Comparison of response in the notch root region with the region away from it

6 Discussions

Totry et. al [10] have demonstrated the complexity in the failure mechanisms which take place under shear in a cross ply laminate and have utilized the computational micromechanical modeling based on multifiber RVE so as to provide a feasible explanation for the observed mechanisms. Some of the important aspects of these mechanisms will be discussed in this section with reference to the results obtained in the previous section. In the micro-macro model developed here the characteristics of two of the failure mechanisms namely matrix failure and fiber-matrix debonding were captured. The full shear response of a cross-ply laminate simulated by the micro-macro method is shown in Fig. 18. There are three distinct regimes of deformation which constitutes the shear response. Initially, there is a linear elastic region wherein the matrix has not yielded. It is followed by a non-linear transition region with decreasing slope and ultimately the stresses continue to rise with an increasing slope. The model is incapable of predicting failure to strain since the fiber breakage is not modeled. As observed in the previous section, the material behavior is not

affected by the presence of stress singularities, therefore the damage mechanisms operating near the notch root concur with those discussed above.

Fig. 18. Figure showing comparison between the response of a laminate and a lamina. The response of shear perpendicular to the fibers is shifted for clarity

Fig. 18 also shows the response of a single lamina predicted by the micro-macro scheme. The geometry is similar to the laminate model discussed in section 4 except that the microstructure now contains fibers only in one direction. The loading and other boundary conditions also remain the same as in the laminate. There are two such geometries possible – one containing fibers in the direction of shear loading and one containing fibers perpendicular to it. As seen in Fig. 18, there is no difference between the response of the lamina in the elastic region under shear parallel and perpendicular to the fibers. The plastic deformation however, showed significant differences in the two modes of shearing. The lamina which is under perpendicular shear shows a very small non-linear region after the elastic portion. This is probably due to the fibers resisting further plastic deformation of the matrix as they have a high bending modulus. The case of fibers in parallel shear also show non-linear region upto 7% strain only before the simulation aborts due to numerical instabilities. However, this lamina shows more plastic deformation than the lamina under perpendicular shear. The reason for this non-extensive plastic deformation of the lamina in parallel shear is that the matrix undergoes most of the deformation and hence the strength of the lamina

becomes almost equal to the shear strength of the matrix.

Fig. 19 shows the accumulated plastic strain in the matrix. It can be seen that the plastic strain accumulates in the form of shear bands in the matrix and is not uniformly distributed in the matrix. These shear bands run parallel to the fibers and interact with each other which leads to the deformation in the matrix. The damage of the fiber-matrix is plotted in Fig. 20. The shear stresses were found to initiate the damage in these elements.

Fig. 19. Contour plot of accumulated plastic strain in the matrix in cross-ply laminate

Fig. 20. Contour plot of damage of the fiber-matrix interface. The value 1 indicates total failure of the interface

7 Concluding remarks

In-plane local shear response of a cross-ply laminate was simulated through a robust micro-macro multiscale scheme. The local response near notch root of a rail shear specimen used in ASTM Standard D7078 was compared with the local response away from the notch root and significant differences were found. Furthermore, it was found that the response to in-plane shear loading is greatly influenced by the properties of the interface present between the fiber and matrix. These important points are summarized as follows:

- The interfacial strength tends to play an important role in determining the overall strength of the composite. A weak interface results in the matrix carrying the entire load and hence the overall strength of the composite reduces while on the other hand a strong interface would improve the overall composite strength
- The shear response near and away from the notch root were similar and it was concluded that the material response of a composite laminate remains unaffected by the presence of stress singularities

The utility of the micro-macro scheme in predicting microscopic stress fields has been successfully demonstrated in this work. This multiscale scheme finds application in solving various other problems such as multi-axial loadings etc. Some of the key features of the scheme are outlined as follows:

- The scheme is applicable to regions with stress singularities without any limitations on the structure
- All the damage mechanisms including delamination can be captured with this scheme
- The coupling between the nodes of the microstructure and macrostructure renders this scheme very sensitive to the mesh density and hence a mesh convergence analysis should be performed to ensure accurate results

8 References

- [1] S. Ghosh, K. Lee and S. Moorthy “Multiple scale analysis of heterogeneous elastic structures using homogenisation theory and Voronoi cell finite element method”. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 32, No. 1, pp 27-62, 1995.
- [2] F. Feyel “A multilevel finite element method (FE²) to describe the response of highly non-linear structures using generalized continua”. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, Vol. 192, No. 28-30, pp 3233-3244, 2003.
- [3] D. Markovic and A. Ibrahimbegovic “On micro-macro conditions for micro scale based FEM for inelastic behavior of heterogeneous materials”. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, Vol. 193, No. 48-51, pp 5503-5523, 2004.
- [4] C. Gonzalez and J. Llorca “Multiscale modeling of fracture in fiber-reinforced composites”. *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 54, No. 16, pp 4171-4181, 2006.
- [5] C. Sun and Y. Wang “Determine the size of local domain in multi-scale analysis”. *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Beijing, paper no. 1681, 2001.
- [6] A. S. D Wang and K.C. Yan “On modeling matrix failures in composites”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 36, No. 10, pp 1335-1346, 2004.
- [7] A. I. Borokov and V. O. Sabadash “Finite Element Multiscale Homogenization and Sequential Heterogenization of Composite Structures”. *Proceedings of 10th Int. ANSYS Conference*, Pittsburgh, paper no. 15, 2002.
- [8] ASTM Standard D7078/D7078M-05, 2000. Standard Test Method for Shear Properties of Composite Materials by V-Notched Rail Shear Method, West Conshohocken, PA, DOI: 10.1520/D7078_D7078M-05, www.astm.org.
- [9] H. Jiang and Y. Xie “A note on the Mohr- Coulomb and Drucker-Prager strength criteria”. *Mechanics Research Communications*, Vol. 38, No. 4, pp 309-314, 2011.
- [10] E. Totry, C. Gonzalez and J. Llorca “Mechanical behavior of composite materials in shear: Experiments and Simulations”. *Anales de Mecánica de la Fractura*, Vol. 1, No. 26, 2009.